

Low Carbon Impact:

Cutting transport emissions with AI insights

Innovate
UK

BridgeAI

CASE STUDY

Low Carbon Impact

Cutting transport emissions with AI insights

“Our proprietary artificial intelligence platform – and how we apply it – is what will set us apart from traditional carbon reduction consultancies,” says Nick Allen, co-founder and CEO of [Low Carbon Impact](#). “It means we can offer affordable, scalable, data-driven advice to companies that have traditionally been starved of this help. It also enables us to deliver this advice without losing the human touch that businesses still need.”

Low Carbon Impact will begin its journey in the transport and logistics sector (although the team sees this as a multiple-sector challenge). This is critical because transport produces around a quarter of the UK’s greenhouse gas emissions. Operators in this sector face growing pressure from customers and regulators to measure, report and reduce their environmental impact. Yet for many, especially small and medium-sized businesses, knowing where to start and how to cut emissions in a commercially viable way, remains a major challenge.

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Nick Allen,
co-founder and CEO of Low Carbon Impact

Credit: freepik.com

Low Carbon Impact is dedicated to tackling this gap. Its AI platform highlights where emissions reductions can be made and its network of experienced decarbonisation advisors turn these insights into clear, practical actions. The result is tailored, actionable plans that help operators cut their carbon footprint while staying competitive.

Low Carbon Impact was matched with AI systems expert Professor Tom Jackson of Loughborough University, whose 20-year-plus research career has included pioneering work on digital decarbonisation. Over a series of advisory sessions, Tom worked closely with the team at Low Carbon Impact to assess their technical approach and provide both strategic and hands-on guidance.

Nick says: “As a startup operating in such a fast-moving environment as artificial intelligence, what matters is having your own ‘Turingista’ to challenge you and keep you honest on your progress against the market and the evolving technology. BridgeAI’s Independent Scientific Advisor offer gave us the chance to bring in expert insight and benchmark what we were doing.”

One of the most valuable interventions concerned Low Carbon Impact’s use of large language models and generative AI. Nick says: “A big takeaway from our sessions with Tom was learning that the quality of the inputs to our platform was a priority ahead of the intricacies of the perfect prompt. That really shifted our approach, and instead of chasing marginal prompt gains, we’ve focused on the embedded quality of our platform to help give us the most compelling outputs. That has probably saved us about 12 months of company time, which is hugely valuable for a small business like ours.”

A semi-truck is shown from a side-rear perspective, driving on a dark asphalt road. The road is flanked by dense, tall green trees, creating a forest-like setting. The lighting suggests a bright day with sunlight filtering through the canopy.

“Working with an Independent Scientific Advisor has been invaluable for us. Tom helped us think differently about how we collect, process and present data so that it delivers real value to our customers. It’s accelerated our technical progress, but more importantly it’s given us the confidence that we’re building something robust, scalable and fit for the market. For a young business like ours, that’s a huge advantage.”

Nick Allen,
co-founder and CEO of Low Carbon Impact

Tom has also helped Low Carbon Impact expand its network in the AI space. An introduction to the Hartree Centre led to a successful application for an innovation voucher, which gave the team access to advanced computational resources and technical support to help understand the parameters of a data quality strategy.

For Tom, the collaboration was a genuine two-way exchange: “Working with Low Carbon Impact was really rewarding. Nick and Martin, the company’s Chief Technical Officer, came to me with a clear vision, but the challenge was making sure their large language model produced meaningful results. Their platform has been architected as a standalone engine, with the aim of giving clients confidence about how their data is handled. That emphasis on privacy and control is a real differentiator compared with mainstream large language models. For me, that combination of strong technical ability, openness to new ideas, and a clear business focus made them a great company to support through the Independent Scientific Advisor offer.”

Looking ahead, Low Carbon Impact aims to extend its platform into new markets and industries, helping accelerate the journey towards net zero in the UK and beyond. “We won’t be a traditional consultancy with AI bolted on the side,” concludes Nick. “AI will be the engine that drives the whole process. We believe that one day all advice will be delivered this way.”

Nick Allen, co-founder and CEO, Low Carbon Impact

About Innovate UK BridgeAI

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

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This work is led by **Dr Vera Matser**, Head of Strategic Capabilities and Principal Investigator for BridgeAI at The Alan Turing Institute.

For any comments, questions, or collaboration opportunities with BridgeAI, please email: bridgeai@turing.ac.uk

Authors and Contributors

Stuart Gillespie: Technical Writer (0009-0003-1402-0184)

Nick Allen: Low Carbon Impact, Co-founder and CEO

Prof Tom Jackson: The Alan Turing Institute, Independent Scientific Advisor for BridgeAI (0000-0001-8404-4251)

Alexandra Araujo Alvarez: The Alan Turing Institute, Senior Research Community Manager (0009-0008-6607-38)

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